

SHORT COMMUNICATION

YIELD RESPONSE OF OKRA TO IRRIGATION FREQUENCY AND AMOUNT IN A SPRINKLER IRRIGATION SYSTEM

Adeogun, E. O.

Department of Land and Water Management Engineering, National Centre for Agricultural Mechanization, Ilorin, Nigeria.

ABSTRACT

*A research study was carried out to determine the most suitable irrigation frequency and amount in okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus L*) production grown under irrigation condition. The research was carried out in a suitable water application method as demonstrated in a sprinkler irrigation system that was established in irrigation research field with a view to determining yield variation and water use efficiency of okra under different irrigation frequencies and amount. Irrigation quantities were based on crop evapotranspiration (ET_{crop}) of the crop (okra) determined at different stages of growth through lysimeter research that was conducted in National Centre for Agricultural Mechanization (NCAM), Ilorin, Nigeria. Analysis of the irrigation evaluations carried out indicated that the yield of fresh fruit of okra was significantly higher under low frequency than high irrigation frequency. A significant reduction in yield was actualized with additional irrigation amount and increase in frequency. It was also estimated that water use efficiency of okra increased to appreciable percentage under low frequency of irrigation. The reduction in water use efficiency under high irrigation frequency as compared to low irrigation frequency resulted primarily from decrease in fresh fruit yield.*

KEYWORDS: Irrigation frequency, amount, water use efficiency, crop water use, relative yield, sprinkler irrigation.

Received for Publication: 11/07/16

Accepted for Publication: 27/11/16

Corresponding Author: manuelaolu2016@gmail.com

All rights reserved

This work by [Wilolud Journals](http://www.wiloludjournal.com) is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/)

INTRODUCTION

The production of okra is globally widespread for its fibrous fruits or pods containing round mature white seeds and leaves, even though it is classified as a primarily a warm season annual vegetable crop grown in tropical and sub-tropical parts of the world. Due to its huge socio-economic potential and being regarded as popularly consumed traditional vegetables, considerable area under cultivation in West and Central Africa (WECA) region accounts for more than 75% of okra produced in Africa with a low average production of 2.5t/ha in the region compare to East (6.2 t/ha) and North Africa (8.8 t/ha) (FAOSTAT, 2008).

Nigeria is considered the largest producer in WECA region where it is traditionally cultivated as a rainy season crop. The awareness of its production under irrigation is encouraged and is being now cultivated as an irrigated crop during the dry season so as to meet with the rapid urbanization and population growth with its market oriented demand. Despite the fact that the world vegetable centre and its partners are poised to undertake long-term research to unlock recognized potential of okra for food, nutrition and income security, okra potential as an industrial crop also has been tested in the developed world and researches are still on-going for its industrial uses as affirmed by Camciuc *et al.*, (1998).

Based on a report by ADP (2005) most producers of vegetables have abandoned irrigation facilities and resorted to hand-watering or furrow methods because of the rising cost of inputs. The adaptability of use of irrigation systems like sprinkler and / or drip irrigation system in Nigeria is still low even though the system is widely considered to have high water use efficient application, as well as relatively low labour and energy cost.

In order to achieve high level of performance and efficiency in using irrigation system for production of okra, the optimization of crop yield both in quality and quantity can be enhanced. The application of irrigation water for okra production during dry season farming has been a major boost for high yield due to high prevalence of sunshine hour that promotes metabolism reaction of photosynthesis.

Irrigation frequency is one of the most important factors in irrigation scheduling. Due to the differences in soil moisture and wetting pattern, crop yields may be different when the same quantity of water is applied under different irrigation frequencies. Typically, the higher the irrigation frequency, the smaller the wetted soil volume and the higher mean soil water content can be maintained in the wetted soil volume during a period when the total irrigation water is equal (Segal *et al.*, 2000).

Several experiments have shown positive responses in some crops to high irrigation frequency (Segal *et al.*, 2000, Sharmasarkar *et al.*, 2001). However, seeming inconsistencies as to what frequency might be optimum can also be found in the literature. Pitts, (1991) found that drip irrigation frequencies (3 times/day, 1 time/day) had no effect on tomato yield. Meshkat *et al.*, (2000) went one step farther by pointing out that an irrigation regime with excessively high

All rights reserved

This work by [Wilolud Journals](#) is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](#)

frequency could cause the soil surface to remain hot with first stage evaporation persisting most of the time resulting in a maximum rate of water loss. Dukes *et al.*, (2003) affirmed that irrigation frequency based on time initiation of irrigation or daily irrigation with different levels of water can affect yield. Some part of the efficiency of irrigation is dependent on air temperature, i.e. warmer temperature cause more evaporation.

In related research carried out, comparisons of different irrigation methods on crop yields and water use efficiency exist (Rouphael *et al.*, 2006), with no or little work carried out so far on the effect of irrigation frequency of a particular irrigation system on the yield. Ones *et al.*, (1995) concluded from his research finding that erroneous irrigation applications underestimate the irrigation time and quantity lead to yield decrease, since water amount required for plants differs for plant growth stage.

The knowledge of application of adequate amount of water needed for plants is essential for development of most suitable irrigation schedule to get optimum plant yield. Ertek *et al.*, (2002) affirmed that erroneous irrigation applications underestimating irrigation amount and quantity may cause yield decrease. It is important to determine the right amount of water supplies needed for plant during the vegetation period, most importantly, the development of most suitable irrigation schedule to produce the optimum plant yield is essential. Yield increase in intensive farming practices during dry season mostly depends on timely and adequate application of irrigation water needed for plant growth. Ertek *et al.*, (2002) affirmed the essentiality of developing the most suitable irrigation schedule to get optimum plant yield.

The objective of this study was to determine how variations in amount and frequency of irrigation affects okra yield grown under irrigated conditions with attendants water use efficiency.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sprinkler irrigation experiments were performed on an area of field comprising nine plots of irrigated okra using a solid-set field equipped with two sprinkler spacing for each plot on an irrigation experimental field of NCAM Integrated Farm Project (NIFAP), Ilorin, Nigeria. The sprinkler nozzle was located at an elevation of 1 m (as a riser level) over the soil surface. The sprinkler rotation was at uniform speed and with the riser perfectly vertical so that the contours of water application rates could be considered as a family of circles having a common centre. An okra crop plantation over an area of 450 m² was established for the experiment and irrigated during the dry season that lasted between December 2015 and March 2016 at a density of 2 – 3 plants m⁻². There are nine plots on the plantation with each plot having an area of 5 m x 10 m. Each plot has one gate valve to control quantity and amount of irrigation water applied during the experiment. An area of a plot for irrigation was given as 50 m² with a controlled flow meter for water measurement on each plot. Irrigation water was applied in measured quantities for different plot under sprinkler irrigation.

All rights reserved

This work by [Wilolud Journals](#) is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](#)

Three irrigation frequency treatments were considered. The experiment was set up with three levels of irrigation frequencies, i.e. $1Ir_1,F_1$, $1Ir_1,F_2$ and $1Ir_1,F_3$ meaning irrigation once in 1-day interval, irrigation once in 2-days interval and irrigation once in 3-days interval respectively. This is preferred because the irrigation of the crop was scheduled to avoid excessive moisture or water stress that could lead to reduced yield, lower quality and plot disease. This three irrigation frequency was replicated twice under different water supply regime of irrigation water supply (ie. $1Ir_2,F_1$, $1Ir_2,F_2$, $1Ir_2,F_3$ and $1Ir_3,F_1$, $1Ir_3,F_2$, $1Ir_3,F_3$) as indicated in Table 1.

Before the okra sprouted, all treatment plots were well irrigated with the same quantity of water at the same frequency in order to ensure a uniform germination rate. After that each plot was irrigated according to prescribed frequency treatments. The discharge rate of the irrigation water supplied to the plot at a given point in time was in order of $2.4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ to $4.12 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$, with an average value of $3.26 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ by the sprinklers.

In determining the amount of water required for a plot, the followings are taken into consideration:

Average coverage diameter for a sprinkler = 6.15 m

Coverage area of the sprinkler = 29.71 m^2

Number of sprinklers per plot = 2

Discharge rate of two sprinklers in a plot = $2.4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$

Discharge rate of one sprinkler in a plot = $4.12 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$

Total coverage area for sprinklers on a plot (G) = 59.42 m^2

Crop evapotranspiration (ET_{crop}) on a plot (50m^2) = $ET_{\text{crop}} \times G$

Crop water demand (ω_c) on a plot = $ET_{\text{crop}} \times K$

(where K is a conversion factor to m^3/s = $6.88 \times 10^{-8} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$)

Therefore, the equation for crop water demand is expressed below:

$$\omega_c = ET_{\text{crop}} \cdot K \quad (1)$$

Crop water data of okra obtained from lysimeter experiment (Adeogun and Ogunlela, 2013) were used in conjunction with irrigation experimental design to determine the crop water demand for a given plot. Irrigation water was administered to the plots under a given percentage of crop water supplied at different sensitive stages.

Water use efficiency of the irrigated okra was determined for this experiment taking into consideration water demanded and water supplied during the experiment. Water use efficiency is defined as the fraction of the total water made available by both rainfall and irrigation that is used by the crop for evapotranspiration (Bos *et al.*, 2005).

All rights reserved

This work by [Wilolud Journals](#) is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](#)

$$\xi_w = \frac{\omega_c}{\phi_s} \quad (2)$$

Where ξ_w is the water use efficiency, ω_c is the crop water demand and ϕ_s is the water supply

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The allocation of water for irrigation was based on values determined from crop water use data obtained from crop evapotranspiration (ET_{crop}) of okra, (Adeogun and Ogunlela, 2013). Water supplied was varied within different plots of okra plantation in the range of 33 %, for Ir₁, 50 % for Ir₂ and 100 % for Ir₃ as additional water required for irrigation. Each sensitivity stage lasted for a decade (ten days) during which same amount of water was supplied to the plots. The irrigation events occurred using a fixed-set sprinkler system covering each experimental plot of 10 m x 5 m.

Analysis of the irrigation evaluations carried out was presented in Table 1. This demonstrated the main characteristics of the irrigation system evaluation performed in the experimental fixed-system during the irrigation of okra. The yield of fresh fruit of okra was significantly higher under low frequency (F₃, ie 3-day irrigation interval) than high irrigation frequency (F₁, ie 1-day irrigation interval). With additional irrigation amount (Ir₂, Ir₃), the yield reduced significantly which resulted in minimum fresh fruit yields. The maximum fruit yield under sprinkler irrigation was observed under Ir₁, F₃. The yield then reduced drastically under Ir₂ and Ir₃ due to considerable increase in irrigation water and frequency.

The data on water use efficiency (WUE) as estimated from fresh fruit revealed that under low frequency of irrigation (F₃), the WUE of okra increased. However, under high frequency irrigation, WUE in F₁ was significantly lower than F₃. The reduction in WUE under high irrigation frequency as compared to low irrigation frequency resulted primarily from decrease in both fresh fruit yield and water use. The WUE of okra increased when the water supplied adequately catered for the water demand by the crop at a given stage of growth. In the event of excess water applied, the WUE decreased. This is due to the fact that okra is not efficient user of water unlike other cereal crops for its production and therefore can thrive well during dry season in as much as the water required at any given stage of growth is adequately supplied.

CONCLUSION

The result of the study demonstrated that the effects of irrigation water amount, plant water consumption and irrigation efficiency are significantly important in order to get the high fruit yield in dry season okra grown under irrigated field condition. Irrigation frequency and crop evapotranspiration significantly affected the fruit yield of okra. Irrigation with 3-day interval had higher yield than those irrigated within 1 to 2 – day interval.

In conclusion, a low irrigation frequency (3-day irrigation interval) with adequate water amount within crop water use value for okra production grown in irrigation condition is recommended

All rights reserved

This work by [Wilolud Journals](#) is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](#)

Table 1: Irrigation frequency and amount of okra in different plots

		Plot 1		Plot 2		Plot 3		Plot 4		Plot 5		Plot 6		Plot 7		Plot 8		Plot 9					
Sensitivity stage		Decade values				I _{r1} , F ₁		I _{r1} , F ₂		I _{r1} , F ₃		I _{r2} , F ₁		I _{r2} , F ₂		I _{r2} , F ₃		I _{r3} , F ₁		I _{r3} , F ₂		I _{r3} , F ₃	
	D	ET _o	ET _{crop}	k _c	ω _c	Q _s	ξ _w																
Establishment (60% of Q_s)	1	80.16	34.7	0.4	2.38	3.84	0.62	3.12	0.76	2.88	0.83	5.22	0.46	4.24	0.56	3.91	0.61	6.59	0.36	5.36	0.44	4.94	0.48
	2	95.63	40.4	0.4	2.78	3.84	0.72	3.12	0.89	2.88	0.97	5.22	0.53	4.24	0.66	3.91	0.71	6.59	0.42	5.36	0.52	4.94	0.56
Vegetative (80% of Q_s)	3	108.82	61.4	0.6	4.22	4.32	0.98	3.36	1.25	3.03	1.39	5.87	0.72	4.56	0.93	4.12	1.02	7.42	0.57	5.77	0.73	5.21	0.81
	4	55.18	34.3	0.6	2.36	4.32	0.55	3.36	0.70	3.03	0.78	5.87	0.40	4.56	0.52	4.12	0.57	7.42	0.32	5.77	0.41	5.21	0.45
Flowering (100% of Q_s)	5	57.17	41.2	0.7	2.83	4.88	0.58	3.6	0.79	3.19	0.89	6.52	0.43	4.89	0.58	4.34	0.65	8.24	0.34	6.18	0.46	5.48	0.52
	6	55.29	31.9	0.6	2.19	4.88	0.45	3.6	0.61	3.19	0.69	6.52	0.34	4.89	0.45	4.34	0.50	8.24	0.27	6.18	0.35	5.48	0.40
Yield formation (80% of Q_s)	7	59.81	9.9	0.2	2.74	4.32	0.63	3.36	0.82	3.03	0.90	5.87	0.47	4.56	0.60	4.12	0.67	7.42	0.37	5.77	0.47	5.21	0.53
	8	50.13	31.1	0.6	2.14	4.32	0.50	3.36	0.64	3.03	0.71	5.85	0.36	4.56	0.47	4.12	0.52	7.42	0.29	5.77	0.37	5.21	0.41
Ripening (60% of Q_s)	9	37.49	13.6	0.4	2.58	3.84	0.67	3.12	0.83	2.88	0.90	5.22	0.49	4.24	0.61	3.91	0.66	6.59	0.39	5.36	0.48	4.94	0.52
Total water supplied					24.22	38.56	63%	30	81%	27.14	89%	52.18	46%	40.74	59%	36.89	66%	65.93	37%	51.52	47%	46.62	52%
Relative yield						0.871		0.976		1.00		0.406		0.781		0.891		0.392		0.472		0.694	

All rights reserved

This work by [Wilolud Journals](http://www.wiloludjournals.com) is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/)

in order to obtain high yield. Also this study was undertaken in order to determine how irrigation frequency and amount affected the crop yield. However, it was found that when irrigation was based on assumed amounts without recourse to crop water use data from crop evapotranspiration, it was not sufficient to produce the best yield. Hence, the need to administer irrigation water based on crop water use data at different growth is important for adequate yield.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The work reported here forms part of a research programme sponsored by National Centre for Agricultural Mechanization (NCAM), Ilorin; on irrigation activities carried out in NCAM Integrated Farm Project (NIFAP) and with due acknowledgement to the Executive Director of the Centre and the staff of the Department of Land and Water Management Engineering for their unflinching support in the course of the work.

REFERENCES

Adeogun, E.O. and A .O. Ogunlela (2013). Determination of Crop Coefficients for Okra Using Lysimetric Evaluation During Dry Season. *Journal of Agricultural Engineering and Technology*, vol. 21(1): 67 – 73.

Agricultural Development Programme (ADP). (2005). Report of monitoring and evaluation Department of the Osun State Agricultural Development Program, OSSADEP/2005/Reports/ Vol. 2, OSSADEP Press, Iwo, Nigeria.

Bos, M. G., M. A. Burton and D.J. Molden (2005). Irrigation and Drainage Performance Assessment. *Practical Guidelines CABI Publishing CAB International Wallingford, OXID 8DE, UK. 158pp.*

Camciuc M, Deplagne M, Vilarem G, Gaset A (1998). Okra-*Abelmoschus esculentus* L. (Moench.), a crop with economic potential for set aside acreage in France. *Industrial Crops Products* 7:257-264.

Dukes, M.D., E.H. Simonne, W.E. Davis, D.W. Studstill, and R. Hochmuth (2003). Effect of sensor-based high frequency irrigation on bell pepper yield and water use. *Proc. Int. Conf. Irrig. Drain.* 2:665–674.

Ertek, A., Sensoy, S., Yıldız, M., Kabay, T., (2002). Estimation of the most suitable irrigation frequencies and quantities in eggplant grown in greenhouse condition by using free pan evaporation coefficient. *K.S. Univ. Life Sci. Eng. J.* 5 (2), 57–67 (in Turkish).

FAOSTAT (2008). Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations. On-line and Multilingual Database, <http://faostat.fao.org/foostat/>

All rights reserved

This work by [Wilolud Journals](#) is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](#)

Meshkat, M., Warner, R.C., Workman, S.R., (2000). Evaporation reduction potential in an undisturbed soil irrigated with surface drip and sand tube irrigation. *Trans. ASAE* 43 (1), 79-86.

Önes, A., Demir, K., Çakmak, B., Kendirli, B., (1995). Drip Irrigation Scheduling in Head Lettuce Grown in Greenhouse Condition (In Turkish). 5. Ulusal Kültürteknik Kongresi Bildirileri, Kemer-Antalya, p. 208.

Pitts, D.J., Tsai, Y.J., Obreza, T.A., Myhre, D.L., (1991). Flooding and drip irrigation frequency effects on tomatoes in South Florida. *Trans. ASAE* 34 (3), 865–870.

Rouphael, Y., M. Cardarelli, E. Rea, A. Battistelli, and G. Colla (2006). Comparison of the sub-irrigation and drip-irrigation systems for green house zucchini squash production using saline and non-saline nutrient solutions. *Agric. Water Manage.* 82:99–117.

Segal, E., Ben-Gal, A., Shani, U., (2000). Water availability and yield response to high frequency micro-irrigation in sunflowers. In: *Proceedings of the Sixth International Micro irrigation Congress on 'Micro-irrigation Technology for Developing Agriculture'*, Conference Papers, 22–27 October, South Africa.

Sharmasarkar, F.C., Sharmasarkar, S., Miller, S.D., Vance, G.F., Zhang, R., (2001). Assessment of drip irrigation and flood irrigation on water and fertilizer use efficiencies for sugarbeets. *Agric. Water Manage.* 46, 241–251.

All rights reserved

This work by [Wilolud Journals](#) is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](#)